

Size-distribution of airborne polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and other organic source markers in the surroundings of a cement plant powered with alternative fuels.

Francisco Sánchez-Soberón^a, Barend L. van Drooge^b, Joaquim Rovira^{a,c}, Joan O. Grimalt^b, Martí Nadal^c, José L. Domingo^c, Marta Schuhmacher^a

^a *Environmental Engineering Laboratory, Departament d'Enginyeria Química, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Av. Països Catalans 26, 43007 Tarragona, Catalonia, Spain*

^b *Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research, CSIC, Jordi Girona 18, 08034 Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain.*

^c *Laboratory of Toxicology and Environmental Health, School of Medicine, IISPV, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Sant Llorenç 21, 43201 Reus, Catalonia, Spain*

Abstract

The distributions of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and molecular tracer organic compounds for biomass combustion, traffic emissions, soil dust, and secondary aerosol processing have been studied in three fractions of ambient air particulate matter (PM₁₀, 2.5, and 1) collected in the vicinity of a cement plant. PAH concentrations were used to estimate the carcinogenic risks in humans. Combustion related compounds, including PAHs, and those from secondary aerosol processing, predominated in the finest (PM<1) fraction, while saccharides related to organic soil dust predominated in the coarse fraction (<PM₁₀). The molecular markers of biomass combustion were found in high concentrations, indicating the influence of biomass burning on PM. Most predominant PAHs were five and six rings species, related to a PAH profile characteristic of urban-industrial environments. The concentrations of benzo[a]pyrene varied between 0.2 and 1.0 ng/m³, which is close but lower than the annual limit value of 1 ng/m³ established by law. Exposure and inhalation carcinogenic risks from total PAHs were below the EPA threshold of acceptable risk (1·10⁻⁶).

Keywords

Cement
Particulate matter
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
Human health risk

Highlights

- >Three fractions of PM (10, 2.5 and 1) were collected nearby a cement plant.
- >Levels of PAHs and other organic compounds were analysed in these fractions of PM.
- >Biomass combustion products were the most prevalent organic compounds.
- >Levels of BaP were relatively high (0.6 ng/m³), but lower than legislation limits.
- >Carcinogenic risks for male and female individuals were considered acceptable.

Abbreviations: AT, averaging exposition time; ATSDR, Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry; BaP, benzo[a]pyrene (BaP); BaPE, benzo[a]pyrene equivalent; BSFTA, bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide; C, concentration; Cal. EPA, Californian Environmental Protection Agency; CF, conversion factor; BW, body weight; ED, exposure duration; EF, exposure frequency; EU, European Union; GC/MS, Gas Chromatography coupled to Mass Spectrometry; IARC, International Agency for Research on Cancer; IR, inhalation rate; L/M, levoglucosan/mannosan ratio; PAH, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon; PM, particulate matter; QFF, quartz fibre filters; SF, slope factor; TEF, Toxicity Equivalency Factors; TMCS, trimethylchlorosilane; USA; United States of America; US EPA, United States Environmental Protection Agency.

1. Introduction

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are generated during incomplete combustion processes (Keyte et al., 2013). Their fused aromatic ring structure (Kamankesh et al., 2015) gives to some of them toxic properties such as cancer and birth failure (ATSDR, 2015; IARC, 2012; US EPA, 2008). Accordingly, outdoor levels of some of these compounds are restricted by legislation (EU Parliament, 2005; US EPA, 2007). Although natural processes such as volcanic eruptions and wildfires release PAHs, anthropogenic sources, such as road traffic, industry, power production, house heating, and incineration (Liao et al., 2011; Manoli et al., 2004; Zhou et al., 2015) are dominating contributors in densely populated areas (Lee and Van Tuan, 2010). The variety of sources, combustion processes, and environmental conditions result in a diversity of PAH distributions (Cecinato et al., 2014; Galarneau, 2008; Sicre et al., 1987). A potential industrial source for PAHs emissions is cement production (García-Pérez et al., 2015; Li et al., 2014). In this process, different amounts of fuel and raw materials are submitted to high temperatures and limited knowledge is available on the influence of different combustion sources, namely alternative fuels, such as sewage sludge or biomass, in the overall PAH production (Conesa et al., 2011).

Airborne PAHs can be present in the gas phase or bound to ambient air particulate matter (PM), depending on the physico-chemical properties of the compound and the meteorological conditions (van Drooge, 2013). Higher PAH levels in PM are typically observed in late autumn and winter, due to lower temperatures, which favours the adsorption of semi-volatile PAHs to PM. This effect, together with lower photochemical degradation of PAHs, and shallower atmospheric mixing layer, results in the accumulation of PAHs in a small air layer (Agudelo-Castañeda et al., 2014; Krůmal et al., 2013; van Drooge, 2013).

Concerning the PAH characteristics, those with highest molecular weight are preferentially linked to the finest PM fraction (Cecinato et al., 2014; Sarigiannis et al., 2015; Varea et al., 2011). Moreover, some of the higher molecular weight PAHs are the most toxic ones, i.e. benzo[a]pyrene (BaP). These two characteristics make PM-bound PAHs specially harmful for health, since submicron PM can enter deep into the respiratory system, and eventually cross the air-blood barrier (Kelly and Fussell, 2012).

Efforts have been made to elucidate source-dependent PAH distributions within different PM fractions, and assessment of their attributable risks to health. Studies in this field are mainly focused on urban-traffic influenced, industrial and indoor environments (Ladji et al., 2009; Liaud et al., 2014; Mesquita et al., 2014; Mirante et al., 2013; Sarigiannis et al., 2015). Only a few studies have considered PM-associated PAHs in the surrounding of cement facilities (Cho et al., 2014; Ercan and Dinger, 2015; Senthilkumar et al., 2014), but they are focused on PM₁₀, which results in a significant lack of information concerning the PAH content and distribution among different sizes of PM, especially the submicron fraction, in areas receiving the emissions from these plants. The European policy promotes the use of alternative fuels for future industrial and domestic applications. (EU Commission, 2014). It is therefore important to study the emissions of installation such as cement plant and to investigate whether other local biomass burning sources may contribute to the particle-bounded PAHs in order to clarify their contributions to ambient PM.

The present study is aimed to improve the knowledge on the contribution of cement plants using alternative fuels to the ambient air PM-associated PAHs, and to assess their potential adverse effects on human health. Three PM fractions (<10, <2.5, and <1 μm) were collected during late autumn in the surroundings of a cement facility located in the outskirts of Barcelona. PAHs and molecular organic tracer compounds, i.e. hopanes for traffic, anhydro-saccharides and dihydroabiatic acid for biomass burning, saccharides for organic soil dust, and dicarboxylic acids for secondary organic aerosol formation, were analysed in these three fractions in order to elucidate the origin of their organic matter constituents. Diagnostic ratios were used for source apportionment. Exposure and human health risks attributable to PAHs were calculated for average male and female adult individuals.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Site description and PM sampling

Descriptions of the area have been provided in previous studies (Rovira et al., 2011; Schuhmacher and Domingo, 2006). Briefly, the studied cement facility is situated in the north of Barcelona. Several industries are active in the area, among them a waste treatment plant. Moreover, two highways with dense traffic in the vicinity of the area as well as the inhabited urban zone. The cement plant has been active since 1917, with a current annual production of about 1 million tons. Owing to the urban development in the surroundings, the distance from the facility to some neighbourhoods has decreased to less than 300 m in the recent years, which increases concern of the administration and public organizations on the possible health impacts of the kiln emissions. Besides fossil fuels, sewage sludge, animal flours, refuse derived fuels, and biomass supply up to 20% of the total energy production are used to power this plant.

Three sampling devices were placed in the roof of a two storey school located 300 m from the cement plant. According to previous studies, this site registers the highest levels of PM in the area, and, therefore, the highest potential health risks (Rovira et al., 2011). Samples were collected during two consecutive weeks comprising the months of November and December of 2014. These days were selected having into consideration results from previous studies, in which major PAH concentrations, and, therefore, maximum risk levels were reached during these days (Mesquita et al., 2014). Meteorological data from this period was obtained from a nearby meteorological monitoring station. Three PM fractions (<10, <2.5 and <1 μm) were collected simultaneously with three high-volume active samplers. PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ were sampled using two TE-6070-DV devices (Tisch Environmental), while PM_1 samples were collected using CAV-A/mb sampler (MCV SA). Daily sampling volumes were 1700 m^3 for PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and around 700 m^3 for PM_1 . PM samples were collected on pre-heated quartz fibre filters (QFF). Before and after sampling, QFF were weighted at room conditions to have an approximate value of PM levels. This procedure was followed in order to minimise PAHs losses after sampling. Finally, filters were wrapped in aluminium foil, and stored at -20°C until further analysis.

2.2. Analytical methods

QFF were ultrasonically extracted in a mixture of dichloromethane and methanol (2:1 (v/v); 3× 20 mL; Merck, Germany) for 15 min. Before extraction 25 µL of surrogate standard succinic acid-D4, levoglucosan-D7 (Cambridge Isotopic Laboratories, UK), anthracene-D10, benz[a]anthracene-D12, benzo[k]fluoranthene-D12, and benzo[ghi]perylene-D12 (Dr. Ehrenstorfer, Germany) were added to samples and blanks. Extracts were then passed through a 0.45-µm Teflon membrane filter (Whatman, USA) to remove particles. Finally, the extracts were concentrated by rotovap to 1 mL.

2.2.1. Analytical procedure for PAHs and hopanes.

Half of the volume of the extract (0.5 mL) was cleaned up by adsorption column chromatography on 1 g of aluminium oxide (Merck, Germany), previously activated at 120 °C overnight. The analytes were eluted with 5 mL of (9:1 v/v) hexane-dichloromethane and 15 mL of (1:2 v/v) hexane-dichloromethane, respectively (Merck, Germany). The collected fractions were concentrated by rotovap to 0.5 mL and further concentrated until almost dryness under a gentle stream of N₂ and diluted in 25 µL of iso-octane (Merck, Germany). An injection standard of 1-phenyldodecane was added before gas chromatographic analysis.

2.2.2. Analytical procedure for saccharides, and dicarboxylic acids.

The analytical methods for these compounds were similar to those described elsewhere (Fontal et al., 2015; Medeiros and Simoneit, 2007). Aliquots of 25 µL of the extract were evaporated to dryness under a stream of N₂. Then, 25 µL of bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (BSFTA) +1 % trimethylchlorosilane (TMCS) (Supelco, USA) and 10 µL of pyridine (Merck, Germany) were added for overnight derivation at room temperature. After that, an injection standard of 1-phenyldodecane was added before gas chromatographic analysis.

2.2.3. Instrumental analyses

Instrumental analyses were carried out by gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (GC/MS). Samples were injected in a Thermo GC/MS equipped with a 60-m fused capillary column (HP-5MS 0.25-mm×0.25-µm film thickness). The oven temperature program started at 60 °C held for 1 min, and then it was heated to 120 °C at 12 °C/min and to 310 °C at 4 °C/min where it was held for 20 min. The injector, ion source, quadrupole, and transfer line temperatures were 280 °C, 200 °C, 150 °C, and 280 °C, respectively. Helium was used as carrier gas at 0.9 mL/s. The MS selective detector operated in full scan (m/z 50–650) and electron impact (70 eV) modes.

PAHs were identified by the following ions: phenanthrene (m/z 178), anthracene (m/z 178), fluoranthene (m/z 202), pyrene (m/z 202), retene (m/z 219), benz[a]anthracene (m/z 228), chrysene (m/z 228), benzo[b]fluoranthene (m/z 252), benzo[k]fluoranthene (m/z 252), benzo[e]pyrene (m/z 252), benzo[a]pyrene (m/z 252), indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene (m/z 276), benzo[ghi]perylene (m/z 276), and coronene (m/z 300). Quantification was performed by calculating the concentrations of the analytes with the external standard calibration curve. The calculated concentrations were corrected for the recoveries of the above-mentioned surrogates: n-C24-d₅₀ (m/z 66), anthracene-d₁₀ (m/z 188), benz[a]anthracene-d₁₂ (m/z 240), benzo[k]fluoranthene-d₁₂ (m/z 264), and

benzo[ghi]perylene-d₁₂ (*m/z* 288). Hopanes were identified with the ion *m/z* 191 and quantified using the relative response of benzo[a]pyrene.

Biomass combustion products, and sugars and derivatives were identified with ion *m/z* 204. Dicarboxylic acids were identified in their derivatized form from the *m/z* 73 and 147 fragmentograms, as well as the individual *m/z* 247, 261, 233, and 295 ions, respectively. Quantification was performed using the external standard calibration curves of levoglucosan and succinic acid. These concentrations were corrected by the recoveries of the surrogate standards d₄-succinic acid (*m/z* 251) and d₇-levoglucosan (*m/z* 206).

2.3. Risk assessment

Preliminary values of human exposure and carcinogenic risks derived from PAHs inhalation were calculated for average 35 years old male and female individuals. The benzo[a]pyrene equivalent (BaPE, in ng/m³) levels for every carcinogenic compound were calculated multiplying concentration of different carcinogenic PAHs (*C_i*, in ng/m³) by Toxicity Equivalency Factors (TEF) provided by US EPA (1993), as expressed in Equation 1:

$$BaPE_i = C_i \times TEF_i \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Exposure (mg/(kg·day)) was calculated as described in Equation 2:

$$Exp = \frac{BaPE_i \times IR \times EF}{BW \times 365} \times CF \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where IR is the Inhalation Rate (m³/day), EF is the Exposure Frequency (days/year), BW is the Body Weight (kg), and CF is the conversion factor (mg/ng). To know carcinogenic risks for the two assessed population groups we adapted equations from previous studies (Sarigiannis et al., 2015) into Equation 3:

$$Cancer\ Risk = Exp \times SF \times ED/AT \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

being ED the exposure duration (years), AT the averaging exposition time (years), and SF the Slope Factor ((kg·day)/mg) for benzo[a]pyrene (BaP) described by Cal. EPA (2011). All parameters used in the above equations are described in Table 1. To calculate the potentially highest carcinogenic risk the model assumed that the total amount of benz[b+j]anthracene was benz[b]anthracene.

Table 1: Parameters used in the exposure and cancer risk calculations.

Parameter	Description	Value		Units	Reference
IR	Inhalation rate	Male	16.88	m ³ /day	US EPA, 2011
		Female	13.68		
EF	Exposure frequency	350		days/year	MAGRAMA, 2007
BW	Body weight	Male	71.5	kg	US EPA, 2011
		Female	58.7		

ED	Exposure duration		35	years	MAGRAMA, 2007
AT	Averaging time		70	years	MAGRAMA, 2007
TEF	Toxic Equivalent Factor	Benzo[a]pyrene	1	unitless	US EPA, 1993
		Benz[a]anthracene	0.1		
		Benzo[b]fluoranthene	0.1		
		Benzo[k]fluoranthene	0.01		
		Chrysene	0.001		
		Dibenz[a,h]anthracene	1		
		Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene	0.1		
SF	Slope Factor	Benzo[a]pyrene	3.90	(kg•day)/mg	Cal. EPA, 2011
	Conversion factor		365	days/year	
CF	Conversion factor		10E-06	mg/ng	
C _i	PAH _i Concentration	Compound Specific		ng/m ³	Present study

2.4. Statistical analysis

Statistical processing was carried out using the statistical software package XLSTAT version 2015.2.02.18681. In order to study correlations among different compounds, Pearson coefficients were calculated. Levene test was performed to elucidate if the data present a parametric distribution. Subsequently, student T tests and ANOVA (parametric data), and Kruskal Wallis (non parametric data) tests were calculated. Correlations and differences were considered significant for probabilities below 0.05 ($p < 0.05$).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Meteorological conditions

During the sampling days, temperatures ranged between 5.8 and 16.5 °C, with an average value of 11.4 °C, relative humidities ranged between 68.4 and 88.9 %, average 78.5 %, and wind speed ranged between 0.9 and 2.1 m/s, average 1.4 m/s. These values fall within the standard climate values recorded in the area for the season (AEMET, 2011). Average wind speeds were light and south west was the predominant direction. No precipitation was registered in sampling days.

3.2. Particulate matter

The average PM concentrations are shown in Table 2. The daily threshold limits established by law are 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM₁₀ (EU Parliament, 2008). This value was exceeded in one sampling day (Fig. 1). Nevertheless, the average PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} levels for the sampling days were below the annual limit values. The PM concentrations obtained in this study were lower than those previously collected in the area (Sánchez-Soberón et al., 2015). About 50% of PM₁₀ were coarse particles ($2.5 < \text{PM} < 10$), while 60 % of PM_{2.5} consisted of submicron particles ($\text{PM} < 1$).

Table 2: Average levels of PM ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and organic compounds (ng/m^3) found in our study.

	PM ₁₀		PM _{2.5}		PM ₁		
	rings	average	desvest	average	desvest	average	desvest
PM		32.10	11.80	15.20	3.37	9.12	3.30

	phenanthrene	3	0.14	0.07	0.10	0.05	0.12	0.05
	retene	3	0.26	0.22	0.19	0.15	0.15	0.11
	fluoranthene	4	0.32	0.16	0.23	0.12	0.24	0.09
	pyrene	4	0.41	0.23	0.29	0.17	0.42	0.21
	benzo[a]anthracene	4	0.61	0.40	0.45	0.31	0.49	0.33
	chrysene	4	0.56	0.31	0.49	0.29	0.59	0.39
PAH	benzo[b+j]fluoranthene	5	1.31	0.82	0.93	0.50	1.08	0.51
	benzo[k]fluoranthene	5	0.35	0.20	0.23	0.11	0.29	0.14
	benzo[e]pyrene	5	0.59	0.31	0.42	0.20	0.50	0.23
	benzo[a]pyrene	5	0.62	0.37	0.43	0.24	0.56	0.35
	indeno[123cd]pyrene	6	0.90	0.47	0.72	0.40	0.91	0.51
	benzo[ghi]perylene	6	1.05	0.51	0.84	0.42	1.15	0.58
	coronene	6	0.16	0.08	0.14	0.08	0.20	0.12
	Total		7.28		5.45		6.69	
Hopanes	17(H) α -21(H) β -29-norhopane		0.20	0.09	0.12	0.05	0.13	0.04
	17(H) α -21(H) β -hopane		0.15	0.05	0.10	0.04	0.09	0.04
	Total		0.35		0.22		0.23	
Biomass combustion products	galactosan		61.17	45.19	43.76	32.81	46.71	38.06
	mannosan		54.32	37.02	39.28	26.61	44.77	31.68
	levoglucosan		518.97	421.59	349.62	278.27	342.75	271.06
	dehydrabietic acid		57.97	43.14	42.77	30.58	47.32	33.69
	Total		692.42		475.43		481.54	
Saccharides and derivatives	α -glucose		52.69	31.50	7.80	6.28	4.52	1.66
	β -glucose		64.88	38.93	10.34	7.59	5.36	1.33
	mannitol		52.62	26.65	9.00	7.72	3.63	1.44
	Total		170.19		27.14		13.51	
Dicarboxylic acids	succinic acid		15.65	4.20	13.61	2.51	14.00	4.96
	glutaric acid		4.02	0.83	3.02	0.82	3.14	0.71
	Total		19.66		16.63		17.14	

3.3. Organic compounds characterization

The concentrations of PAHs and other organic compounds are reported in Table 2. The sampling variability of the different compounds is shown in Fig. 1. Except for the saccharides, no statistical significant differences were observed in the concentrations of the analysed organic compounds among the three PM fractions, indicating that they are predominantly present in the submicron fraction (PM₁), which is in agreement with other studies (Degrendele et al., 2014; Liaud et al., 2014), including those performed in the urban area of Barcelona (Aceves and Grimalt, 1993; van Drooge and Grimalt, 2015).

3.3.1. PAHs

The predominant PAHs in the PM samples contained five and six rings, namely benzo[b+j]fluoranthene and benzo[ghi]perylene. These compounds have also been identified as predominant PAH in other urban-industrial environments (Varea et al., 2011). No statistical significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were found when comparing PAH distributions by number of rings in the three analyzed fractions, which is consistent with a predominance of all PAHs in the submicron fraction (PM₁). According to previous studies (Manoli et al., 2004), emissions from cement plants are characterized by a

relatively high contribution of 3 rings compounds up to 30% of total PAHs mass. Previous studies performed near cement plants (Ercan and Dincer, 2015) also showed a high proportion of three ring PAHs. In the samples collected in the present study, this percent contribution of 3 rings PAHs (i.e. phenanthrene and retene) was 5%, indicating that PAH in the collected samples were likely exposed to atmospheric aging and partitioning between gas and particles. These processes are of high importance for lower molecular PAHs. Isomeric ratios of PAH can be used as diagnostic ratios for emissions, although caution should be taken on the interpretations due to the influence of environmental factors as well as variable emissions of PAHs from the same sources (Galarneau, 2008). Comparison of these values in PM₁₀ with previous studies, they were more similar to those reported for incinerators or gasoline cars than to cement plants (Table 3) (Cecinato et al., 2014; Sicre et al., 1987). This result could be a consequence of the use of alternative fuels (biomass, sewage sludge) in the cement plant. However, as mentioned before, the diagnostic ratios are variable depending on photooxidation rate, source type, and combustion conditions (Galarneau, 2008). They could also reflect that the PAH input from the cement plant do not predominate over other nearby sources such as the two highways, the waste treatment plant and several industries. Retene, a methyl-PAH and molecular tracer compound for (pine) wood combustion (Ramdahl, 1983), was found in all samples and at considerable concentrations ranging from 0.05 to 0.7 ng/m³, and showing significant correlations with the other PAHs compounds (0.18<R²<0.74; p<0.05). The strongest correlation was observed for benz[a]anthracene, while the weakest correlation for benzo[ghi]perylene, which are two PAH compounds that are related to wood burning and (diesel) car emissions, respectively.

Table 3: PM₁₀-PAHs diagnostic ratios in present study and for different sources as reported previously (Cecinato et al., 2014)

	Present Study	Cement stack	Incinerator stack	Straw burning	Pine wood burning	Diesel car	Gasoline car
BaA/(BaA+BaP)	0.50	0.38	0.55	0.58	0.60	0.84	0.44
Chy/(BaP+Chy)	0.47	0.40	0.59	0.60	0.70	0.89	0.47
BaA/(BaA+Chy)	0.53	0.48	0.46	0.48	0.39	0.39	0.48
Flu/(Flu+Pyr)	0.44	0.68	0.56	0.55	0.54	0.52	0.49

BaA: benzo[a]anthracene; BaP: benzo[a]pyrene; Chy: chrysene; Flu: fluoranthene; Pyr: pyrene

Regarding weekly patterns, no statistical significant differences ($p>0.05$) were found in PAH concentrations when comparing weekdays and weekends. Previous studies performed in Barcelona showed the same trend (van Drooge et al., 2012b). The concentrations of total PAHs in this study were about two times higher than those observed in the urban background of the city of Barcelona in the same season (Mesquita et al., 2014). However, they were within the range of those recorded in other urban Mediterranean areas (Sarigiannis et al., 2015). In this study, the average levels of BaP (0.6 ng/m³) and BaP-equivalents (0.9 ng/m³) in PM₁₀ were slightly lower than the 1 ng/m³ the annual limit established by the European Union in the directive 2004/107/EC (EU Parliament, 2005), indicating that despite an influence of additional emission sources, such as the cement plant, the limit values are not exceeded in the studied urban area. Nevertheless, the relatively high BaP levels justify a source apportionment study to estimate the contribution of the potential emission sources.

3.3.2. *Hopanes*

Hopanes are found in lubricating oil of engines from diesel and gasoline powered vehicles and are used as traffic markers (Křůmal et al., 2013; van Drooge et al., 2012a). The concentrations of these compounds ranged between 0.1 and 0.2 ng/m³, with no statistical significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between weekdays and weekends. These levels were lower than those recorded previously in Barcelona in winter, suggesting a small influence from traffic sources in the collected particles (van Drooge et al., 2012a).

3.3.3. *Biomass combustion products*

Levoglucosan, an anhydro-saccharide from thermal alternation of celluloses, was the prevalent organic compound in the analysed samples, showing about 8 times higher concentrations than its isomers (mannosan and galactosan). The concentrations of PM₁₀ levoglucosan ranged from 147 to 1300 ng/m³, while mannosan and galactosan ranged from 19 to 150 ng/m³. No statistical significant differences were observed among the three PM fractions, indicating that these compounds were predominantly in the submicron fraction. Levoglucosan, mannosan and galactosan have been identified as markers of biomass burning, essentially wood burning (Kourtchev et al., 2011). The ratio levoglucosan/mannosan (L/M) can be used to identify the wood type. In the present study, the L/M ratios ranged from 7.5-9.5, which is intermediate between softwood (3.5-4.0) and hardwood (14-15) (Schmidl et al., 2008). The presence of dehydroabietic acid is characteristic of softwood combustion and is consistent with these intermediate levels. In any case, the concentrations of biomass combustion products were much higher than those observed in previous studies in Barcelona, but similar to those collected in regional areas of Catalonia and other Mediterranean cities during winter (Giannoni et al., 2012; Jedynska et al., 2015; Sarigiannis et al., 2014; van Drooge, 2013; van Drooge et al., 2012a) suggesting that biomass burning emissions are influencing air quality in the studied area, probably more than traffic emissions.

3.3.4. *Saccharides and derivates*

Saccharides and derivates were mainly found in the coarse ($2.5 < PM < 10$) fraction. The concentrations of glucose (α and β) found in this study ranged from 43 to 259 ng/m³ in PM₁₀, while PM_{2.5} and PM₁ showed values between 6 and 52 ng/m³. These levels were higher than those previously found in Mediterranean sites in winter (Pietrogrande et al., 2014). The lack of correlation between these components and the rest of the organic compounds suggests an origin different than combustion. Saccharides are related to wood smoke and soil resuspension (Schmidl et al., 2008). The lack of correlation between concentrations of saccharides and the other markers of biomass burning suggests a predominant source related with soil resuspension as the main origin of saccharides. Previous studies from this area (Sánchez-Soberón et al., 2015) showed that most mineral components of these airborne particles are found in the coarse fraction. Accordingly, soil resuspension is the main likely origin of these saccharides. Mannitol is a sugar alcohol used as marker of bioactivity, since it is a common storage substance in fungal spores (Bauer et al., 2008). The concentration of this component in our study were higher than registered previously in Barcelona during summer, but lower than those recorded in Easter Mediterranean regions in autumn (Burshtein et al., 2011; van Drooge et al., 2012b). These differences could be related to the life cycle of fungus, since autumn is the season of maximum fungal reproduction.

3.3.5. Dicarboxylic acids

Dicarboxylic acids have been previously recognised as markers of secondary organic aerosols in the absence of biomass combustion (Hallquist et al., 2009). The concentrations of succinic acid were higher than glutaric acid (Table 2), since the former is one of the major acid compounds present in PM (Hsieh et al., 2008). The concentrations of this dicarboxylic acid were similar to those previously recorded in Barcelona in same season (van Drooge et al., 2012a). While secondary organic aerosols in this study were mainly located in the PM₁ fraction, secondary inorganic aerosols previously collected in the area had similar contribution for every PM fraction (Sánchez-Soberón et al., 2015). This could suggest different origins and formation processes between these two components or that part of the dicarboxylic acids could originate from primary sources such as biomass burning.

Fig. 1: Daily levels of PM, PAHs and other organic compounds.

3.4. Risk assessment

Exposure and carcinogenic risk were evaluated for the seven carcinogenic PAHs recognized by the U.S. E.P.A (US EPA, 1993), among these dibenz[a,h]anthracene was not detected in the present study. Since PAHs were essentially in the PM₁ fraction, this fraction contributed the most to exposure and carcinogenic risk, reaching a value of $2.04 \cdot 10^{-7}$ mg BaPE/(kg·day). PM₁ was responsible of more than 94% of this value. Consequently, overall cancer risk were higher for male individuals, reaching a PM₁₀ value of $3.98 \cdot 10^{-7}$ (Fig.2), involving about 4 cases of cancer due to PAH inhalation for

every 10^7 inhabitants. BaP was the compound that exhibited the highest exposure and carcinogenic activity, contributing about 70% of the overall exposure and cancer risk values. Carcinogenic risk due to PAHs inhalation was below the threshold of acceptable risk established by the U.S. E.P.A. as $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ (one case of cancer for every 10^6 inhabitants) (US EPA, 1996).

Fig. 2: Carcinogenic potential for the three PM fractions and PAHs compounds. Error bars depict total standard deviation.

4. Conclusions and implications

In this study three fractions of PM (<10 , <2.5 , and $<1 \mu\text{m}$) were collected in the vicinity (300 m) of a cement plant in late autumn, the period of the year in which highest PM levels are normally recorded. Daily limits of PM_{10} were exceeded only one day, while the average levels of PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ were below the legal thresholds. Organic compounds (except saccharides) were predominantly found in the finest PM_1 fraction. Biomass combustion products were the most prevalent organic compounds, reaching higher levels than those found in Barcelona metropolitan area. This result evidences high contributions of local biomass burning in the studied area. The most predominant PAHs were five and six rings species with a PAH profile characteristic of a mixture of urban and industrial environments. The concentrations of benzo[a]pyrene were relatively high (0.6 ng/m^3), but below the limit set by the European Union (1 ng/m^3). Health risk to the population after exposure to ambient air PAHs in the area was 4 cases of cancer per 10^7 inhabitants, which is below the EPA threshold ($1 \cdot 10^{-6}$).

Acknowledgments

This study was financed by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO), as part of the project CTM2012-32778. F. Sánchez-Soberón received a doctoral scholarship as part of the project above mentioned. The authors also want to thank LAFARGE CEMENTOS SAU their help while sampling.

Bibliography

- Aceves, M., Grimalt, J.O., 1993. Seasonally dependent size distributions of aliphatic and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in urban aerosols from densely populated areas. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 27, 2896–2908. doi:10.1021/es00049a033
- AEMET, 2011. Standard climate Values: Barcelona, Fabra - Agencia Estatal de Meteorología - AEMET. Gobierno de España.
- Agudelo-Castañeda, D.M., Teixeira, E.C., Calesso Teixeira, E., Teixeira, E.C., 2014. Seasonal changes, identification and source apportionment of PAH in PM1.0. *Atmos. Environ.* 96, 186–200. doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2014.07.030
- ATSDR, 2015. Toxic Substances Portal - Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) [WWW Document]. URL <http://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/PHS/PHS.asp?id=120&tid=25> (accessed 2.26.15).
- Bauer, H., Claeys, M., Vermeylen, R., Schueller, E., Weinke, G., Berger, A., Puxbaum, H., 2008. Arabitol and mannitol as tracers for the quantification of airborne fungal spores. *Atmos. Environ.* 42, 588–593. doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2007.10.013
- Burshtein, N., Lang-Yona, N., Rudich, Y., 2011. Ergosterol, arabitol and mannitol as tracers for biogenic aerosols in the eastern Mediterranean. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 11, 829–839. doi:10.5194/acp-11-829-2011
- Cal. EPA, 2011. Technical Support Document for Cancer Potency Factors: Methodologies for derivation, listing of available values, and adjustments to allow for early life stage exposures. Appendix A.
- Cecinato, A., Guerriero, E., Balducci, C., Muto, V., 2014. Use of the PAH fingerprints for identifying pollution sources. *Urban Clim.* 10, 630–643. doi:10.1016/j.uclim.2014.04.004
- Cho, Y., Kim, G.-B., Cho, Y.-S., Choi, M.S., Ryu, S.-H., Choi, S.H., Park, Y.-K., Choi, J.W., 2014. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons exposure in residents living near a cement factory with kilns. *Int. Arch. Occup. Environ. Health* 87, 889–896. doi:10.1007/s00420-014-0931-z
- Conesa, J.A., Rey, L., Egea, S., Rey, M.D., 2011. Pollutant formation and emissions from cement kiln stack using a solid recovered fuel from municipal solid waste. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 45, 5878–5884. doi:10.1021/es200448u
- Degrendele, C., Okonski, K., Melymuk, L., Landlová, L., Kukučka, P., Čupr, P., Klánová, J., 2014. Size specific distribution of the atmospheric particulate PCDD/Fs, dl-PCBs and PAHs on a seasonal scale: Implications for cancer risks

- from inhalation. *Atmos. Environ.* 98, 410–416.
doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2014.09.001
- Ercan, Ö., Dincer, F., 2015. Atmospheric concentrations of PCDD/Fs, PAHs, and metals in the vicinity of a cement plant in Istanbul. *Air Qual. Atmos. Heal.*
doi:10.1007/s11869-015-0314-y
- EU Commission, 2014. State of play on the sustainability of solid and gaseous biomass used for electricity, heating and cooling in the EU. Brussels.
- EU Parliament, 2008. Directive 2008/50/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2008 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe. *Off. J. Eur. Communities.* 152, 1–44.
- EU Parliament, 2005. Directive 2004/107/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 December 2004 relating to arsenic, cadmium, mercury, nickel and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in ambient air. *Off. J. Eur. Communities.* 23, 3–16.
- Fontal, M., van Drooge, B.L., López, J.F., Fernández, P., Grimalt, J.O., 2015. Broad spectrum analysis of polar and apolar organic compounds in submicron atmospheric particles. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1404, 28–38.
doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2015.05.042
- Galarneau, E., 2008. Source specificity and atmospheric processing of airborne PAHs: Implications for source apportionment. *Atmos. Environ.* 42, 8139–8149.
doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2008.07.025
- García-Pérez, J., López-Abente, G., Castelló, A., González-Sánchez, M., Fernández-Navarro, P., 2015. Cancer mortality in towns in the vicinity of installations for the production of cement, lime, plaster, and magnesium oxide. *Chemosphere* 128C, 103–110. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.01.020
- Giannoni, M., Martellini, T., Del Bubba, M., Gambaro, A., Zangrando, R., Chiari, M., Lepri, L., Cincinelli, A., 2012. The use of levoglucosan for tracing biomass burning in PM_{2.5} samples in Tuscany (Italy). *Environ. Pollut.* 167, 7–15.
doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2012.03.016
- Hallquist, M., Wenger, J.C., Baltensperger, U., Rudich, Y., Simpson, D., Claeys, M., Dommen, J., Donahue, N.M., George, C., Goldstein, A.H., Hamilton, J.F., Herrmann, H., Hoffmann, T., Iinuma, Y., Jang, M., Jenkin, M.E., Jimenez, J.L., Kiendler-Scharr, A., Maenhaut, W., McFiggans, G., Mentel, T.F., Monod, A., Prévôt, A.S.H., Seinfeld, J.H., Surratt, J.D., Szmigielski, R., Wildt, J., 2009. The formation, properties and impact of secondary organic aerosol: current and emerging issues. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 9, 5155–5236. doi:10.5194/acp-9-5155-2009
- Hsieh, L.-Y., Chen, C.-L., Wan, M.-W., Tsai, C.-H., Tsai, Y.I., 2008. Speciation and temporal characterization of dicarboxylic acids in PM_{2.5} during a PM episode and a period of non-episodic pollution. *Atmos. Environ.* 42, 6836–6850.
doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2008.05.021

IARC, 2012. IARC Monographs - Volume 100F.

Jedynska, A., Hoek, G., Wang, M., Eeftens, M., Cyrus, J., Beelen, R., Cirach, M., De Nazelle, A., Keuken, M., Visschedijk, A., Nystad, W., Akhlaghi, H.M., Meliefste, K., Nieuwenhuijsen, M., de Hoogh, K., Brunekreef, B., Kooter, I.M., 2015. Spatial variations of levoglucosan in four European study areas. *Sci. Total Environ.* 505, 1072–81. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.10.091

Kamankesh, M., Mohammadi, A., Hosseini, H., Modarres Tehrani, Z., 2015. Rapid determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in grilled meat using microwave-assisted extraction and dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction coupled to gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Meat Sci.* 103, 61–7. doi:10.1016/j.meatsci.2015.01.001

Kelly, F.J., Fussell, J.C., 2012. Size, source and chemical composition as determinants of toxicity attributable to ambient particulate matter. *Atmos. Environ.* 60, 504–526. doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2012.06.039

Keyte, I.J., Harrison, R.M., Lammel, G., 2013. Chemical reactivity and long-range transport potential of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons--a review. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 42, 9333–9391. doi:10.1039/c3cs60147a

Kourtchev, I., Hellebust, S., Bell, J.M., O'Connor, I.P., Healy, R.M., Allanic, A., Healy, D., Wenger, J.C., Sodeau, J.R., 2011. The use of polar organic compounds to estimate the contribution of domestic solid fuel combustion and biogenic sources to ambient levels of organic carbon and PM_{2.5} in Cork Harbour, Ireland. *Sci. Total Environ.* 409, 2143–55. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2011.02.027

Křůmal, K., Mikuška, P., Večeřa, Z., 2013. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and hopanes in PM₁ aerosols in urban areas. *Atmos. Environ.* 67, 27–37. doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2012.10.033

Ladji, R., Yassaa, N., Balducci, C., Cecinato, A., Meklati, B.Y., 2009. Distribution of the solvent-extractable organic compounds in fine (PM₁) and coarse (PM₁₋₁₀) particles in urban, industrial and forest atmospheres of Northern Algeria. *Sci. Total Environ.* 408, 415–24. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2009.09.033

Lee, B.-K., Van Tuan, V., 2010. Sources, Distribution and Toxicity of Polyaromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) in Particulate Matter, in: Villanyi, V. (Ed.), *Air Pollution*. Sciyo. doi:10.5772/269

Li, C., Nie, Z., Cui, S., Gong, X., Wang, Z., Meng, X., 2014. The life cycle inventory study of cement manufacture in China. *J. Clean. Prod.* 72, 204–211. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.02.048

Liao, C.-M., Chio, C.-P., Chen, W.-Y., Ju, Y.-R., Li, W.-H., Cheng, Y.-H., Liao, V.H.-C., Chen, S.-C., Ling, M.-P., 2011. Lung cancer risk in relation to traffic-related nano/ultrafine particle-bound PAHs exposure: a preliminary probabilistic assessment. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 190, 150–158. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2011.03.017

- Liaud, C., Dintzer, T., Tschamber, V., Trouve, G., Le Calvé, S., 2014. Particle-bound PAHs quantification using a 3-stages cascade impactor in French indoor environments. *Environ. Pollut.* 195, 64–72. doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2014.08.007
- MAGRAMA, 2007. Guía Técnica de aplicación del RD 9/2005, de 14 de enero, por el que se establece la relación de actividades potencialmente contaminantes del suelo y los criterios y estándares para la declaración de suelos contaminados. [WWW Document]. URL http://www.magrama.gob.es/es/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/temas/suelos-contaminados/guia_tecnica_contaminantes_suelo_declaracion_suelos_tcm7-3204.pdf (accessed 9.25.14).
- Manoli, E., Kouras, A., Samara, C., 2004. Profile analysis of ambient and source emitted particle-bound polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons from three sites in northern Greece. *Chemosphere* 56, 867–878. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2004.03.013
- Medeiros, P.M., Simoneit, B.R.T., 2007. Analysis of sugars in environmental samples by gas chromatography–mass spectrometry. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1141, 271–278. doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2006.12.017
- Mesquita, S.R., van Drooge, B.L., Reche, C., Guimarães, L., Grimalt, J.O., Barata, C., Piña, B., 2014. Toxic assessment of urban atmospheric particle-bound PAHs: relevance of composition and particle size in Barcelona (Spain). *Environ. Pollut.* 184, 555–562. doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2013.09.034
- Mirante, F., Alves, C., Pio, C., Pindado, O., Perez, R., Revuelta, M.A., Artiñano, B., 2013. Organic composition of size segregated atmospheric particulate matter, during summer and winter sampling campaigns at representative sites in Madrid, Spain. *Atmos. Res.* 132-133, 345–361. doi:10.1016/j.atmosres.2013.07.005
- Pietrogrande, M.C., Bacco, D., Visentin, M., Ferrari, S., Casali, P., 2014. Polar organic marker compounds in atmospheric aerosol in the Po Valley during the Supersito campaigns — Part 2: Seasonal variations of sugars. *Atmos. Environ.* 97, 215–225. doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2014.07.056
- Ramdahl, T., 1983. Retene—a molecular marker of wood combustion in ambient air. *Nature* 306, 580–582.
- Rovira, J., Mari, M., Schuhmacher, M., Nadal, M., Domingo, J.L., 2011. Monitoring environmental pollutants in the vicinity of a cement plant: a temporal study. *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 60, 372–384. doi:10.1007/s00244-010-9628-9
- Sánchez-Soberón, F., Rovira, J., Mari, M., Sierra, J., Nadal, M., Domingo, J.L., Schuhmacher, M., 2015. Main components and human health risks assessment of PM10, PM2.5, and PM1 in two areas influenced by cement plants. *Atmos. Environ.* 120, 109–116. doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2015.08.020
- Sarigiannis, D.A., Karakitsios, S.P., Kermenidou, M., Nikolaki, S., Zikopoulos, D., Semelidis, S., Papagiannakis, A., Tzimou, R., 2014. Total exposure to airborne

- particulate matter in cities: the effect of biomass combustion. *Sci. Total Environ.* 493, 795–805. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.06.055
- Sarigiannis, D.A., Karakitsios, S.P., Zikopoulos, D., Nikolaki, S., Kermenidou, M., 2015. Lung cancer risk from PAHs emitted from biomass combustion. *Environ. Res.* 137, 147–156. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2014.12.009
- Schmidl, C., Marr, I.L., Caseiro, A., Kotianová, P., Berner, A., Bauer, H., Kasper-Giebl, A., Puxbaum, H., 2008. Chemical characterisation of fine particle emissions from wood stove combustion of common woods growing in mid-European Alpine regions. *Atmos. Environ.* 42, 126–141. doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2007.09.028
- Schuhmacher, M., Domingo, J.L., 2006. Long-term study of environmental levels of dioxins and furans in the vicinity of a municipal solid waste incinerator. *Environ. Int.* 32, 397–404. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2005.09.002
- Senthilkumar, S., Manju, A., Muthuselvam, P., Shalini, D., Indhumathi, V., Kalaiselvi, K., Palanivel, M., Chandrasekar, P.P., Rajaguru, P., 2014. Characterization and genotoxicity evaluation of particulate matter collected from industrial atmosphere in Tamil Nadu state, India. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 274C, 392–398. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2014.04.017
- Sicre, M.A., Marty, J.C., Saliot, A., Aparicio, X., Grimalt, J., Albaiges, J., 1987. Aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons in the mediterranean aerosol. *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.* 29, 73–94. doi:10.1080/03067318708078412
- US EPA, 2011. Exposure Factors Handbook: 2011 Edition, National Centre of Environmental Assessment, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Washington, D.C., U.S.A. Sept. 2011.
- US EPA, 2008. Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) [WWW Document]. URL <http://www.epa.gov/osw/hazard/wastemin/minimize/factshts/pahs.pdf>
- US EPA, 2007. Benzo(a)pyrene (BaP) TEACH Chemical Summary.
- US EPA, 1996. Soil screening guidance: technical back- ground document.
- US EPA, 1993. Provisional guidance for quantitative risk assessment of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons.
- Van Drooge, B.L., 2013. Human Exposure to Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons in Urban and Rural Ambient Air, in: Occurrence, Fate and Impact of Atmospheric Pollutants on Environmental and Human Health. pp. 59–82. doi:10.1021/bk-2013-1149.ch004
- Van Drooge, B.L., Crusack, M., Reche, C., Mohr, C., Alastuey, A., Querol, X., Prevot, A., Day, D.A., Jimenez, J.L., Grimalt, J.O., 2012a. Molecular marker characterization of the organic composition of submicron aerosols from Mediterranean urban and rural environments under contrasting meteorological conditions. *Atmos. Environ.* 61, 482–489. doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2012.07.039

- Van Drooge, B.L., Grimalt, J.O., 2015. Particle size-resolved source apportionment of primary and secondary organic tracer compounds at urban and rural locations in Spain. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 15, 7735–7752. doi:10.5194/acp-15-7735-2015
- Van Drooge, B.L., Lopez, J.F., Grimalt, J.O., 2012b. Influences of natural emission sources (wildfires and Saharan dust) on the urban organic aerosol in Barcelona (Western Mediterranean Basin) during a PM event. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res. Int.* 19, 4159–4167. doi:10.1007/s11356-012-0890-4
- Varea, M., Galindo, N., Gil-Moltó, J., Pastor, C., Crespo, J., Gil-molt, J., Pastor, C., Crespo, J., 2011. Particle-bound polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in an urban, industrial and rural area in the western Mediterranean. *J. Environ. Monit.* 13, 2471–2476. doi:10.1039/c1em10163c
- Zhou, H., Wu, C., Onwudili, J.A., Meng, A., Zhang, Y., Williams, P.T., 2015. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) formation from the pyrolysis of different municipal solid waste fractions. *Waste Manag.* 36, 136–46. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2014.09.014